

Online Service Equality in Public Libraries

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ABSTRACT

With the rise of the Black Lives Matter movement in 2020, the American Library Association revised its Code of Ethics to increase awareness of and recommend actions to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion. Still, given that past research into library service equality shows mixed findings, there is a need today more than ever before to examine if public libraries provide equitable online reference services. Based on an analysis of over one thousand email responses, we found that public libraries provided equal service to all users regardless of their gender and race most of the time; however, females received significantly more and friendlier responses than male users, and White users received more emails than Black users. White female users also received the most emails while Black male users received the least.

KEYWORDS

Public Libraries; Virtual Reference Services; Racial Discrimination; Gender Discrimination

INTRODUCTION AND RELATED RESEARCH

Service discrimination based on gender and race has been a major social concern. While the Black Lives Matter movement in 2020 raised awareness of diversity, equality, and inclusion among librarians, there is still a need to examine whether discrimination in online reference services provided by public libraries exists, as evidence of online inequality in other sectors is plentiful (e.g., Cui et al., 2020; Leite et al., 2021; Sabbah et al., 2019). For example, service discrimination was found on Airbnb, showing that requests from guests with perceived Black names were less likely to be accepted than those with perceived White names (Cui et al., 2020). Additionally, in healthcare settings, racial and gender-based discrimination was associated with a reduced likelihood of medical visits by individuals from targeted groups (Leite et al., 2021; Sabbah et al., 2019).

Research on library service discrimination includes mixed results (Hamer, 2021; Shachaf & Horowitz, 2006; Shachaf et al., 2008; Vladoiu & Fichman, 2022). One study showed that inquiries from users with Arab and Black names were more likely to be ignored, have longer wait times, receive lower quality responses, and lack high level of professionalism than White names (Shachaf & Horowitz, 2006). Another study reported equitable services to diverse users in response time, reliability, and courtesy, regardless of user gender or ethnicity (Shachaf et al., 2008). Recent studies found evidence of implicit ethnic bias displayed in virtual reference interactions and while one favored Black users the other did not (Hamer, 2021; Vladoiu & Fichman, 2022). The first study conducted in academic libraries in England found that Black African users received the lowest quality of service overall (Hamer, 2021), while the second study conducted in the United States (US) found that Black users received more answers to their inquiries than White users (Vladoiu & Fichman, 2022).

However, because prior research provides evidence for gender bias online (Asplund et al., 2020; Grapin et al., 2022), it is possible that gender bias among Black or White users will be evident. Since librarianship is a pink-collar profession (Howe, 1977) dominated by female workers (ALISE 2022 Statistical Report, 2022), gender bias in online services may not exist. It is likewise possible that gender bias will result in favorable online library service to female users, because according to the theory of ethnic and gender concordance, individuals prefer to interact with people of the same race or gender (Malat & van Ryn, 2005).

Thus, there is a dire need for more research into online library service equality in American public libraries, given the mixed findings of past research, the recently revised ALA Code of Ethics, and the demographics of librarians. Our study aims to address this gap and answer the research question: Do public libraries in the US provide equitable online services to the public regardless of race (Black/White) or gender (Female/Male)?

METHOD

Study Design

We designed a two-by-two unobtrusive field experimental study to determine whether public libraries provide equal email reference services to users of different genders and races, as represented by their names. The names that we used have been previously utilized previously (e.g., Shachaf et al., 2008): Emily Baker (White female), Latoya Jones (Black female), Todd Kelly (White male), and Tyrone Jackson (Black male).

Data Collection

We randomly selected a sample of 251 American public libraries using the American Library Directory Online, from a sample list that included 6,168 public libraries across the US. To account for variations in question difficulty

that may impact service quality, we used the counter balanced method to send out email requests, so that every library received each of the four inquiries only once and received all four types of questions. By doing so we accounted for the possible impact of question difficulty on our results. At the same time, gender and race manipulation was equally balanced across all libraries. The only difference between libraries in each of the four sets of libraries was the order in which they received the questions over time (Table 1).

	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
First set of libraries	Question 1 from White Female	Question 2 from Black Female	Question 3 from White Male	Question 4 from Black Male
Second set of libraries	Question 2 from White Female	Question 3 from Black Female	Question 4 from White Male	Question 1 from Black Male
Third set of libraries	Question 3 from White Female	Question 4 from Black Female	Question 1 from White Male	Question 2 from Black Male
Fourth set of libraries	Question 4 from White Female	Question 1 from Black Female	Question 2 from White Male	Question 3 from Black Male

Table 1. Counter-balanced method of email sending

We modified the questions from Shachaf et al. (2008) and sent these questions: (1) What was the population of [town in which library is located] in 2020? (2) Does your library have Romeo and Juliet? (3) Can you help me find some resources about growing and taking care of rosebushes? (4) What is the average temperature in May in London?

Between September 19, 2022, and October 7, 2022, we sent out 1,004 email requests to 251 libraries from four Gmail accounts. Once a week, we sent emails on Mondays and collected all emails responses received before midnight on Friday of that week.

Data Analysis

We used Nvivo for data analysis and used a codebook with seven codes in two categories: politeness and answer quality (Table 2); the codebook was a modification of Shachaf et al. (2008).

Code	Description	Example
Politeness	Professional behavior indicators	
First name	Librarian addresses user by first name	“Tyrone”
Greeting	Librarian greets the user	“Hello”, “Good morning”
Follow up	Librarian invites the user to follow up or ask another question	“Please let us know if there is anything else we can find for you.”
Closing	Librarian adds a closing the end of the response with/without their name	“Best”, “Sincerely”, “Thank you”
Answer	Answer quality indicators	
Question answered	The question was answered by the librarian	“Yes, we do own Romeo and Juliet!”
Verifiability	Librarian provides the information source/ URL	“I found the information from this travel site. [URL]”
Multiple resources	Librarian provides multiple resources with relevant information	“Here are a few helpful links I found.”

Table 2. Codebook

We also examined responsiveness level, by counting the number of libraries who replied to our inquiry (regardless of whether the question was answered in their response) [=Response Rate] and by counting the number of days before a response was received [=Timely Response]. Finally, we examined the extent of correspondence by counting the number of emails received in the whole thread of emails from a library to a user [=Emails], regardless of whether the question was answered or not.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

We discuss our findings in two sections. First, we focus on responsiveness and timely responses, and then we report our answer quality and politeness results. In each section, we report the differences based on race, gender, and the interaction effect of race by gender.

We found no significant differences in the response time based on gender, race, or gender by race (Table 3); all users, regardless of race or gender receive a timely response, within a day most of the time, echoing prior research (Shachaf et al., 2008). We found that librarians provide timely responses to their users, with a high percentage of same day responses, which is what is expected by most customers in the US (Faria, 2023). We also found no significant differences based on race in terms of the number of replies users received to their questions, but we found significant differences based on gender; females were significantly more likely to get a reply from public libraries than male users (Table 3).

	Qs		Emails		Response Rate			Timely Response								
	N	N	χ^2	N	%	χ^2	Same day			Next day			Later			
							N	%	χ^2	N	%	χ^2	N	%	χ^2	
Emily Baker	251	148	9.45*	127	50.6	5.98	100	78.7	5.8	24	18.9	4.28	3	18.9	4.94	
Latoya Jones	251	121		112	44.6		79	70.5		23	20.5		10	20.5		
Todd Kelly	251	128		107	42.6		84	78.5		13	12.1		10	12.1		
Tyrone Jackson	251	116		101	40.2		77	76.2		18	17.8		6	17.8		
Female	502	269	2.49	239	47.6	3.88*	179	74.9	1.44	47	19.6	3.56	13	19.6	0.32	
Male	502	244		208	41.4		161	77.4		31	14.9		16	14.9		
White	502	276	6.06*	234	46.6	1.78	184	78.6	3.49	37	15.8	0.22	13	15.8	0.32	
Black	502	237		213	42.4		156	73.2		41	19.2		16	19.2		

Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)

Table 3. Response rate, timely response, and emails in correspondence

Interestingly, we found a significant gender by race interaction effect in the total number of emails received by the four users (Table 3). White female users received significantly more emails while Black male users received significantly less emails than other users. Looking at the number of emails users received, our results are consistent with prior studies that racism and sexism are not independent (Seaton & Tyson, 2019). However, while others found that Black males received better service than Black females (Seaton & Tyson, 2019; Vladoiu & Fichman, 2022), our findings are in contrast, showing Black males do not receive service that is as good as other users. Interestingly, when it comes to the main effect, we found that in the number of emails received gender differences were not statistically significant, but racial differences were (Table 3); significantly more emails have been sent from the public librarians to White users than to Black users (276 vs. 237, respectively). Our findings support previous research that found racial discrimination in online services, where Black people were less likely to receive replies in social media-based customer services (Gunarathne et al., 2019).

Moreover, we found that females got better service than males also in the inclusion of a closing (Table 4); librarians included a closing in their responses to female users significantly more often than in their responses to male users (124 vs. 92, respectively). Our findings are consistent with prior study that males seem to suffer more negative impact of discrimination than females (Seaton, Caldwell, Sellers, & Jackson, 2008), males are more likely to be treated unfriendly. Overall, however, public librarians provide equal service to all users regardless of race or gender on all other three politeness and three answer quality measures, supporting Shachaf et al. (2008)'s results.

Category	Code		Gender*Race				Gender		Race	
			Emily Baker	Latoya Jones	Todd Kelly	Tyrone Jackson	Female	Male	White	Black
Answer	Resources	N	21	25	21	22	46	43	42	47
		χ^2	0.53				0.11		0.31	
	Answered	N	111	107	98	95	218	193	209	202
		χ^2	2.78				2.57		0.20	
	Verifiability	N	37	31	19	30	68	49	56	61
		χ^2	6.53				3.49		0.24	
Politeness	Closing	N	66	58	46	46	124	92	112	104
		χ^2	6.80				6.04*		0.38	
	Follow up	N	31	28	24	20	59	44	55	48
		χ^2	2.98				2.43		0.53	
	Greeting	N	70	68	71	63	138	134	141	131
		χ^2	0.77				0.08		0.50	
	First name	N	60	48	51	43	108	94	111	91
		χ^2	3.79				1.21		2.48	
Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)										

Table 4. Answer quality and politeness

In sum, we found that most of the time public librarians in the US provide equitable service to their users, regardless of race and gender, and adhere to their professional code of ethics. Our findings support earlier findings from the US (Shachaf et al., 2008) but contradict recent findings from England (Hamer, 2021). The English study shows that Black African users received the lowest quality of service overall, and thus future research to examine service equality in other countries or other ethnicities is still needed. Still, we found traces of gender, racial and intersectional biases, where females and Whites are more likely to get better service than males and Black. The theory of gender and race concordance could provide partial explanation of our findings, because White female librarians are dominant the US (ALISE 2022 Statistical Report, 2022), and they may carry a bias toward other White females to their service provision.

CONCLUSION

Our study provides clear evidence of largely equal public library reference service, while prior research showed mixed findings. Public libraries provided equal service to all users regardless of their gender and race most of the time. However, female users received significantly more and friendlier emails than male users did; the librarians also interacted more with White female users than they did with Black male users. While this bias might be unintentional, it is evident in our findings. Indeed, we provide evidence for one of the major concepts of critical race theory, intersectionality, showing the interaction of gender and race in the traces of biased service that public libraries in the US provided online in 2022. While critical race theorists (CRT) reject the idea “color blindness”, they acknowledge the persistence of racial disparities in the United States and raise structural questions about how racist hierarchies are enforced, even among people with good intentions, such as librarians in public libraries. Like other proponents of CRT that understand race as a creation of society, a socially constructed concept rather than a biological reality, we argue that it is important to display the stories people who experience racism.

Our results that female users received more responses and friendlier responses than male users should raise librarians' attention to the fact that they provide favorable services to females than males, and that this may exacerbate the lower level of male use of library services (Applegate, 2008; Merga & Roni, 2017). Identifying inequalities in library services may inform the development of inclusive library policies and practices to help librarians in their effort to further minimize inequality and better serve diverse communities. In addition, library administrators may strive to build up a more diverse service team.

One of the study limitations is that we assumed most of the librarians who replied to our requests are White females, but future research should examine this assumption. Future research may examine service equality to other user groups (e.g., other races, religions, and non-binary genders), as well as expand the study of the equality of online services provided by other types of organizations beyond libraries.

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